

SHARIA FINANCIAL SERVICES COOPERATIVES (KJKS): MAPPING RESEARCH TOPICS USING VOSVIEWER BIBLIOMETRIC AND LIBRARY RESEARCH ANALYSIS

Hellen Monica Ghaby Ayu Saputra, Eka Wahyu Hestya Budianto

Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang, Indonesia

Corresponding author: hellenmonica@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the development of research around Sharia Financial Services Cooperative. The research was conducted from 2009 to 2022, by searching national journals indexed by Sinta via the Garuda website, with the keyword "Sharia Financial Services Cooperative". Based on the search results, there were 142 research articles, then inputted into the VOSviewer application and analyzed descriptively through a Library Research study. The results showed that the number of publications had increased significantly every year. Furthermore, based on the results detected using the VOSviewer application, research related to Sharia Financial Services Cooperative is divided into 5 clusters and 93 items. Meanwhile, based on the results of a Library Research study, there are 6 main themes related to Sharia Financial Services Cooperative.

Keywords: *Sharia Financial Services Cooperative, Bibliometrics, VOSviewer, Library Research*

I. INTRODUCTION

Very fast developments in various developed and developing countries require financial institutions, such as banks, as a place to carry out financial transactions. Financial institutions have an important role in a country's economy. At this time, many financial institutions are starting to operate differently from conventional banks, one of which is sharia cooperatives. Sharia cooperatives do not charge interest and do not burden customers, but receive profit sharing in accordance with the agreed contract. Micro businesses sometimes experience difficulties in raising business capital and investment. The Sharia Financial Services Cooperative (KJKS) exists as a lending institution by collecting funds on a rolling basis for its cooperative members, namely micro businesses. Sharia Financial Services Cooperative (KJKS) is a cooperative that operates in the financial sector using sharia principles.

In previous research, before the KJKS existed, lower middle class people often had to borrow money from loan sharks or conventional savings and loan institutions at high interest rates to increase capital for small businesses. The Small Business

Incubation Center (PINBUK) then created KJKS-BMT as an innovative solution to this problem. Research related to KJKS has also been carried out in various institutions and companies in various regions. Apart from the principle of mutual assistance, there are other principles that must be adhered to in the KJKS operational system, namely based on Islamic sharia. This system prohibits collecting or borrowing money with additional interest (*riba*), as stated in the Qur'an and Hadith which states that usury is haram. In Indonesia, KJKS first appeared in 1992 and has experienced quite rapid development since then. According to data from the Indonesian Ministry of Cooperatives and SMEs, the number of KJKS in Indonesia continues to increase from year to year. In 2010, there were around 1,767 KJKS throughout Indonesia, while in 2020, the number of KJKS had reached 3,852 units. This development is in line with increasing public interest in sharia financial services which are considered more ethical and in accordance with Islamic principles. Apart from that, the government is also encouraging the development of KJKS through policies that are profitable for cooperatives. In 2014, the Indonesian government launched the New Cooperative Movement (GKB) program which aims to increase the role of cooperatives in the national economy. One of the focuses of this program is the development of sharia cooperatives, including KJKS. The government also provides various incentives and institutional support for KJKS, such as increasing access to financing and expanding the cooperative network. With government support and increasing public interest in sharia financial services, the development of KJKS in Indonesia is still continuing and is expected to continue to grow in the future.

Based on search results via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital), there are 145 studies on KJKS in Indonesia until 2022. The aim of this research is to map the development of research on KJKS in Indonesia using the VOSviewer bibliometric study method and e-review literature study.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Sharia Financial Services Cooperative (KJKS) is a cooperative operating in the financial services sector that follows sharia principles. KJKS functions to facilitate the economic activities of the community, both as a financial institution and a social institution. KJKS provides various financial services in accordance with sharia principles, such as financing for micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs), sharia savings, sharia investment and sharia insurance. KJKS also ensures that all its business activities are carried out in a halal manner and in accordance with Islamic law. As a cooperative-based financial institution, KJKS also applies the principles of togetherness and independence, where cooperative members play an active role in managing and obtaining benefits from KJKS' business activities. KJKS is also expected to help improve community welfare through sustainable economic empowerment.

Bibliometric studies are a research method that uses bibliographic and literature analysis to measure and evaluate the impact, productivity, and relationship between scientific works and their authors. This method can be used to observe trends in scientific publications, identify collaborations between researchers, measure the level of influence and citations of a work, and analyze network structures in scientific

literature (Dubyna et al., 2022). One software that is often used in bibliometric studies is VOSviewer. This software helps researchers in analyzing and visualizing bibliographic data such as citations, author affiliations, and keywords. With VOSviewer, researchers can create scientific network maps that show connections between elements in bibliographic datasets. The visualization helps in identifying relevant patterns, clusters, and trends in the scientific literature. Users can build network maps based on keywords, authors, or institutions, and see the relationships between these elements visually and intuitively. With VOSviewer, users can recognize clusters of adjacent research, highlight the most influential authors, view collaboration networks between researchers, as well as analyze changes over time. In addition, VOSviewer also provides various bibliometric metrics such as number of citations, h-index, or frequency of certain keywords in the dataset.

Library Research study is a systematic and comprehensive research process on relevant literature that already exists in a particular field of knowledge or topic. The main purpose of a Library Research study is to identify, evaluate, and synthesize research that has been previously conducted by experts in the field. In a Library Research study, researchers will search, read, and analyze various sources of information such as scientific journals, books, theses, dissertations, conferences, and other publications that are relevant to the topic being researched. They will collect and evaluate data from the literature, such as research findings, methodology used, and conclusions reached.

III. METHODOLOGY

In this research, a mix-method approach was used which combines quantitative methods and qualitative methods. Quantitative methods are used in bibliometric studies, while qualitative methods are used in Library Research studies. The focus of this research is Sharia Financial Services Cooperatives (KJKS). The data used is secondary data obtained from scientific publication articles about KJKS originating from national and accredited journals. The data source was obtained from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). Data analysis tools used include Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, VOSviewer, and Perish.

The data collection technique consists of several steps, namely: (1) Visiting the Garuda website and using Perish software to search for relevant journal titles with the keywords "KJKS" and "Sharia Financial Services Cooperative" in the time period from 2009 to 2022; (2) Data on journal titles was collected in Microsoft Excel and then duplicate titles were identified; (3) RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) files from the collected journals are downloaded; and (4) The RIS data file is entered into the software Mendeley Desktop.

The data analysis technique includes several steps, namely: (1) mapping RIS data files analyzed and grouped by year, author and publisher using Mendeley Desktop; (2) mapping bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using VOSviewer software, taking into account the number of clusters and items. (3) mapping topics, methods, research findings, and research gaps based on Library Research studies.

IV. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Sharia Financial Services Cooperatives (KJKS)

Search results for scientific publications regarding KJKS from 2009 to 2022 show a decrease in publications, especially in 2021, namely 7 articles.

Table 1. Scientific publication data about KJKS by year

Year of Publication	Number of Publication	Year of Publication	Number of Publication	Year of Publication	Number of Publication
2009	1	2014	21	2019	20
2010	0	2015	13	2020	16
2011	1	2016	11	2021	9
2012	6	2017	14	2022	4
2013	11	2018	15		
Total 142					

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

In table 2, there are 115 institutions/affiliations related to KJKS. The Economic Journal is the largest journal publisher that publishes research results regarding KJKS, with 19 articles. Meanwhile, the BUSINESS Journal reached 16 articles.

Table 2. Ranking of institutions and journals publishing scientific publications regarding KJKS

Name of Affiliate/Institution	Number of Publications
Economic Journal _	19
BUSINESS	16
Iqtishadia: Journal of Sharia Economics and Banking	5
Research journal	4
Accounting and Management, Al-Qanun: Journal of Islamic Legal Thought and Reform, El-Qist: Journal of Islamic Economics and Business, Scientific Journal of Islamic Economics, Journal of Scientific Accounting Studies UNTAN Faculty of Economics (Kiafe)	3
Accounting: Integrative Accounting Journal, Al - Muzara'ah, Encyclopedia of Journal, IQTISHADUNA, Islamic Economics Journal, FEB Student Scientific Journal, Business Administration Science Journal, Equatorial Education and Learning Journal, J Group Law Faculty Student Journal, Maqdis: I slam Economic Studies Journal, Muqtasid: Sharia Economics and Banking Journal, QULUBANA: Management Journal Da'wah	2

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

The most productive researchers around KJKS are Eni Noor Fitriana, Kevry Ramadany, Dewi Sartika, Ady Wena Pramudya Sukmaningrum, and Puji Sucia, each of whom wrote 2 journal articles. Meanwhile, other researchers only wrote 1 journal article.

4.2 Mapping Research Topics Regarding Sharia Financial Services Cooperatives (KJKS) using the VOSViewer Bibliometric Study

Article search results on the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) are exported in RIS (Research Information Systems) format, input and analyzed using VOSviewer software. The results are as follows:

Figure 1. Network visualization of research development map around KJKS

Source: Processed data, software VOSViewer 1.6.18.

The network visualization map of research developments regarding KJKS in Sharia Financial Institutions are divided into 5 clusters and 93 topic. The results are as follows:

- Cluster 1. The red color consists of 27 topics, namely: approach, principle, rule, activity, system, quality, sharia, abstract, analysis, investment, product, kinship, agreement, contract, existence, community, aspect, question, Indonesia, period, role, question, cooperative, regulation, agreement, data analysis.
- Cluster 2. The green color consists of 16 topics, namely: research, service, technique, performance, central Java, customer satisfaction, effect, influence, t test, keywords service quality, respondent, company, saving, amount, significant effect, respondent.
- Cluster 3. The blue color consists of 22 topics, namely: data, kjk, customer, liquidity, person, capital, loan, provision, ability, person, business, development,

need, data, time, application, venture capital, system, process, condition, information, capital.

- Cluster 4. The yellow color consists of 17 topics, namely: interview, observation, primary data, research, solution, case, documentation, management, factors, implementation, lack, manager effort, research, assessment, primary data, secondary data, analysis technique, impact, sharia financial services coop.
- Cluster 5. The purple color consists of 11 topics, namely: study, analysis, financing, bmt, party, effort, financing, organization, data collection technique, data analysis technique, murabahah.

4.3 Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding problems in Sharia Financial Services Cooperatives (KJKS)

Library Research study in previous research journals, there are 15 problems with Sharia Financial Services Cooperatives/KJKS, namely:

First, procedures and resolution of financing problems. The following are the procedures and resolution of problematic financing at KJKS: (1) KJKS must identify problems in problematic financing that occur, this is done to find out the type of problem that occurs and its causes; (2) KJKS must contact members who have financing problems, and provide solutions and explanations regarding the problems that occur and discuss ways to resolve them; (3) KJKS must hold discussions with members who have financing problems to find the best solution for both parties, for example, discussing rescheduling installment payments or restructuring financing; (4) If deliberation does not produce a solution, then KJKS can resolve it through legal channels, which can be done if members are not cooperative in resolving problematic financing issues; (5) KJKS must take preventive measures so that problematic financing problems do not occur again in the future, one of which is to carry out a more thorough credit evaluation before providing financing to members; and (6) KJKS must report problematic financing to the competent authorities, such as the Sharia Financial Services Authority (OJK Syariah) and the Cooperative and Small and Medium Enterprises Supervisory Agency (BPKS). This is done so that problems can be resolved quickly and precisely.

Second, analyze the competitors of Sharia Financial Institutions. To conduct a competitor analysis of Sharia Financial Institutions in the Sharia Financial Services Cooperative (KJKS), here are several steps that can be taken:

- (1) Identify competitors. The first step that must be taken is to identify competitors who are the target of comparison. In this case, you must identify KJKS that are similar to the Sharia Financial Institution that you want to analyze. After identifying competitors, you can obtain information about the products, services and strategies they use to compete with Islamic Financial Institutions.
- (2) Identify strengths and weaknesses. The next step is to identify the strengths and weaknesses of the selected Islamic Financial Institution and competitors. Strengths and weaknesses can relate to products, services, operations, marketing, etc. By identifying the strengths and weaknesses of each financial

- institution, you can find out where Sharia Financial Institutions have advantages or weaknesses in competing with competitors.
- (3) Market analysis. The next step is to conduct a market analysis to obtain information about market conditions, opportunities and threats faced by Sharia Financial Institutions and competitors. You can use market data obtained from third party sources such as market research institutions or related media.
 - (4) Evaluate competitor strategies. The next step is to evaluate the identified competitors' strategies. This evaluation can help you understand what strategies competitors are using, whether it is product, marketing, distribution or other strategies. You can also find out how competitors respond to market conditions and how they change their strategies in response to changes in the market.
 - (5) Identify opportunities and threats. Based on the results of analysis and evaluation, you can identify opportunities and threats faced by Sharia Financial Institutions. Opportunities may be related to market growth, changes in consumer behavior, or favorable government policies. While threats can be related to intense competition, adverse changes in government policy, or changes in consumer behavior.
 - (6) Action plan. The final step is to create an action plan based on the results of the analysis and evaluation that has been carried out. This action plan may take the form of developing new products or services, improving marketing or promotions, or increasing operational efficiency. Action plans must be designed to strengthen the advantages of Islamic Financial Institutions and overcome weaknesses, while still taking advantage of opportunities and facing threats faced in the market.

Third, sharia life insurance. Sharia life insurance and the Sharia Financial Services Cooperative (KJKS) are closely related because both are sharia financial institutions based on sharia principles. Sharia life insurance is a type of insurance that operates in accordance with sharia principles, such as no elements of usury (interest), speculation, or gharar (uncertainty). Sharia life insurance offers financial protection to participants in the event of the risk of death, disability or illness which could affect their income and financial condition. Meanwhile, the Sharia Financial Services Cooperative (KJKS) is a cooperative that operates in the sharia finance sector and provides financial services to its members. KJKS aims to promote financial practices that are in line with sharia principles, such as not allowing usury, not engaging in speculation, and not taking unclear risks. The link between sharia life insurance and KJKS is that KJKS can provide sharia life insurance services to its members as a form of financial service they offer. In this case, KJKS acts as an intermediary between participants and sharia life insurance companies. In practice, KJKS can offer sharia life insurance with lower premiums compared to conventional life insurance products. This is because in sharia life insurance, participants contribute to sharia investment funds which are invested in a halal manner. The investment results can be used to pay claims or can be returned to participants in the form of cash value.

Fourth, *takaful family*. One of the products offered by KJKS is *family takaful*, which is a sharia insurance program that protects families from unexpected financial risks such as death, permanent disability or critical illness. *Takaful family* involves participants paying premiums regularly, and if one of them experiences a protected risk, the *takaful* benefits will be paid to the family of the participant exposed to the risk. In this context, KJKS acts as a provider of *family takaful* programs offered to its members. In this way, KJKS becomes a means to access *family takaful* products that are trustworthy and in accordance with sharia principles. In this case, collaboration between KJKS and *takaful* companies is important to ensure that the *family takaful* program offered by KJKS meets sharia requirements and provides optimal benefits for its members.

Fifth, the capital loan received by KJKS from Sharia Bank. One form of financial service provided by KJKS is capital loans for micro and small businesses. If KJKS needs funds to provide capital loans to its customers, then one source of funding that can be utilized is Sharia Bank. The following are several steps that are usually taken in the process of receiving a KJKS capital loan from a Sharia Bank: (1) *Capital Loan Request*, namely KJKS submits a capital loan application to a Sharia Bank. This application must contain details of the loan amount, intended use, loan term, and collateral to be provided. (2) *Feasibility Analysis*, namely the Sharia Bank carries out a feasibility analysis of the capital loan application submitted by KJKS. Feasibility analysis includes analysis of KJKS' financial performance, completeness of application documents, and KJKS' ability to fulfill loan repayment obligations. (3) *Loan Offer*, namely after a feasibility analysis is carried out, Sharia Bank provides a loan offer to KJKS. This offer must contain details of the interest rate, administration fees, loan term, and other conditions that must be met by KJKS. (4) *Signing of the Loan Agreement*, namely if KJKS agrees with the loan offer provided by Sharia Bank, then both parties will sign the loan agreement. This agreement will contain details of the loan amount, loan term, interest rate, collateral provided, and other provisions that must be fulfilled by KJKS. (5) *Loan disbursement*, namely after the loan agreement is signed, Sharia Bank will disburse the loan to KJKS. The loan amount will be adjusted as agreed in the agreement, and will be transferred to the KJKS account. (6) *Loan repayment*, namely KJKS must pay loan installments according to the time period agreed in the agreement. If KJKS cannot pay the loan installments on time, KJKS will be subject to fines or other sanctions in accordance with the provisions of the agreement.

Sixth, the existence and role of KJKS. KJKS has an important role in the economic development of the people, especially in Indonesia, where the majority of the population is Muslim. The existence of KJKS itself is very important because it is an alternative for people who want to use financial services with sharia principles. In the sharia economic system, there are principles that must be followed, such as no interest in financial transactions, no speculation, and not being based solely on profit. KJKS is an institution that bridges sharia principles with the financial needs of its members. The role of KJKS itself is very important in economic development, especially in areas that are still underdeveloped or underdeveloped. KJKS can

provide loans to its members to start a business, so that it can help improve the welfare of its members and the surrounding community. KJKS can also provide financial education to its members, so that it can help increase knowledge and awareness about the importance of good and correct financial management.

Seventh, Mudharabah financing risk management. The following are several steps that can be taken by KJKS in risk management for Mudharabah financing: (1) Risk Evaluation, namely KJKS must identify risks related to Mudharabah financing, such as credit risk, liquidity risk, market risk and operational risk. KJKS must measure and evaluate the level of risk to take appropriate action to manage it. (2) Determination of Policies and Procedures, namely KJKS needs to establish clear policies and procedures in carrying out Mudharabah financing. This includes procedures for managing funds, requirements for potential debtors, risk control, and collection procedures. (3) Selection of the Right Debtor, namely KJKS must select the right debtor candidate who meets the specified requirements. This can help reduce credit risk and strengthen the ability of potential debtors to repay Mudharabah financing. (4) Financing Feasibility Assessment, namely KJKS needs to carefully assess the financing feasibility before providing Mudharabah financing. This includes analysis of business feasibility, ability to generate profits, and ability to repay financing. (5) Credit Risk Control, namely KJKS needs to control credit risk by managing the amount of financing provided and monitoring the repayment of financing regularly. (6) Financing Portfolio Diversification, namely KJKS needs to diversify its financing portfolio to reduce credit risk and strengthen its financial position. This is done by spreading risk across different business sectors. (7) Liquidity Management, namely KJKS needs to carry out liquidity management by taking into account short-term and long-term funding needs. This can help reduce liquidity risk and ensure smooth KJKS operations. (8) Supervision and Monitoring, namely KJKS needs to carry out regular supervision and monitoring of the Mudharabah financing that has been provided. This includes monitoring financing repayment, fund management and financial reporting.

Eighth, application of the Hawalah agreement to problematic financing. The implementation of the Hawalah agreement on problematic financing at KJKS can be done in several steps, including:

- (1) Identify problematic financing. KJKS needs to identify problematic financing first before the Hawalah agreement can be implemented. Financing that is considered problematic is financing that has passed the payment deadline, has a high risk of default, or financing made by customers who have a bad credit history.
- (2) Agreement between KJKS and customers. After problematic financing is identified, KJKS and the customer can make an agreement to transfer the debt through a Hawalah agreement. In this agreement, KJKS and the customer must determine the party who will be the recipient of the debt or receivables (*muqayyid*), the amount of debt that will be transferred, and the period for transferring the debt.

- (3) Implementation of the Hawalah contract. After the agreement is made, KJKS can carry out the Hawalah agreement by transferring the debt in writing or verbally to the party who has been agreed to be the muqayyid. KJKS can submit financing agreement documents and hand over the claim rights for the debt to the muqayyid.
- (4) Debt repayment. After the debt is transferred to the muqayyid, the customer can pay off the debt to the muqayyid in accordance with the agreement that has been made. Muqayyid will receive payments from customers and provide payment confirmation to KJKS.

Ninth, member default in the loan agreement. The following are several possible legal consequences that could occur if a KJKS member defaults on a loan agreement: (1) Fines, namely if a KJKS member violates the terms and conditions of the loan agreement, he can be subject to a fine. The amount of the fine is usually determined by the KJKS in the loan agreement, and can vary depending on the type of violation committed. (2) Loan termination, namely KJKS has the right to terminate the loan if the member defaults. In this case, members must immediately pay off all loan obligations, including interest, fines and other fees. (3) Account blocking, namely KJKS has the right to block a member's account if he is in default. This means that members cannot carry out other transactions with KJKS until they have paid all their obligations. (4) Legal demands, namely if members do not immediately pay off their obligations, KJKS has the right to sue the members legally. KJKS can file a lawsuit in court to collect member debts. (5) Access restrictions, namely if a member violates the loan agreement, KJKS can limit the member's access to the products and services provided by KJKS.

Tenth, the handling of Murabahah financing is problematic. The following are several steps for handling problematic Murabahah financing at KJKS:

- (1) Initial Evaluation. KJKS must carry out an initial evaluation of problematic Murabahah financing, namely by examining the causes and severity of the problem. This evaluation aims to find out whether the financing can still be completed or whether it requires further resolution.
- (2) Contact with Borrower. After finding out the cause of the problem, KJKS must immediately contact the borrower to discuss solutions. In this case, KJKS can provide several options such as restructuring or extending payment terms.
- (3) Restructurisation. Restructuring is an option that can be carried out by KJKS to resolve problematic Murabahah financing. Restructuring is carried out by changing the terms and conditions of financing, so that borrowers can repay according to their ability.
- (4) Extension of Payment Time. KJKS can also extend the payment period as an option to resolve problematic Murabahah financing. In this case, KJKS provides additional time for borrowers to repay the financing in accordance with the agreed agreement.
- (5) Settlement Through Court. If efforts to restructure or extend payment terms are unsuccessful in resolving problematic Murabahah financing, KJKS can

take steps to resolve it through the courts. In this case, KJKS can file a lawsuit in court to resolve the dispute with the borrower.

- (6) Buy-Back (Buy-Back). If all efforts to resolve problematic Murabahah financing are unsuccessful, KJKS can carry out a buy-back on the goods that are the object of financing. In this case, KJKS buys back the goods from the borrower and resells the goods to reduce the financial losses incurred.

Eleventh, the risk of default on Mudharabah financing. The risk of default on Mudharabah financing at KJKS can occur due to several factors such as: (1) Poor business performance: If the customer's business is not running well and experiences significant losses, it is likely that the customer will have difficulty paying back the funds that have been borrowed. This can cause the risk of default on Mudharabah financing. (2) Not complying with the rules: Customers who do not comply with the rules in the Mudharabah agreement, such as not using funds in accordance with the financing objectives or not paying back the funds at the specified time, can cause the risk of default on the financing. (3) External factors: External factors such as poor economic conditions, natural disasters, or changes in government policy can affect customers' ability to repay the funds they have borrowed. This can also cause the risk of default on Mudharabah financing. To reduce the risk of default on Mudharabah financing, KJKS can take several actions such as: (1) Carry out a careful credit risk analysis before providing financing to customers; (2) Have an effective monitoring and supervision mechanism for customer business performance and the use of borrowed funds; (3) Provide financing only to customers who have good business performance and are proven capable of paying back the funds they have borrowed; (4) Diversifying risks by providing financing to several different business sectors; (5) Setting a reasonable and fair interest rate to prevent customers from having difficulty paying back the funds they have borrowed; and (6) Have a clear and firm agreement regarding the customer's obligations in repaying the funds that have been borrowed.

Twelfth, the influence of government recommendations on strengthening KJKS institutions. This is because the government has the authority to provide direction, regulations and support in various forms to financial institutions such as KJKS. One form of government recommendation that can influence the KJKS institution is the legal and regulatory policies that regulate the KJKS. With clear and detailed statutory regulations, it is hoped that KJKS can obtain legal certainty and be able to operate effectively. The government can also provide fiscal and non-fiscal incentives to KJKS that meet certain criteria, such as lower taxes or loan interest subsidies. Apart from that, the government can also provide financial and technical support to KJKS through the assistance programs provided. This assistance program can help KJKS strengthen its institutions, such as management training, product and service development, or providing business capital. In this case, government recommendations related to financial and technical support can help KJKS to strengthen its institutions and increase its competitiveness in the market. Government support can also help improve KJKS' performance in providing financial services to the community, especially those who have not been reached by conventional financial institutions.

Thirteenth, comparison with Savings and Loans Cooperatives/KSP. In general, KJKS has several differences with KSP: (1) Sharia principles, namely KJKS operates with sharia principles, which follow Islamic rules such as the prohibition of usury (interest), speculation and gambling. Meanwhile, KSP does not follow sharia principles. (2) Products and Services, namely KJKS provides products and services that comply with sharia principles, such as murabahah, mudharabah, musyarakah financing, etc. Meanwhile, KSP provides loan services with normal interest and collateral. (3) Membership, namely KJKS is limited only to Muslims and people who agree to follow sharia principles. Meanwhile, KSP is open to everyone regardless of religion, gender or social background. (4) Supervision, namely KJKS is supervised by the Sharia Financial Services Authority (OJK Syariah), while KSP is supervised by the Cooperative and Small and Medium Enterprises Supervisory Agency (BPKP). (5) Capital and Profits, namely KJKS uses a profit sharing system, where profits are shared between members and the cooperative. Meanwhile, KSP uses an interest system, where profits are obtained from the difference between the interest given to borrowers and the interest earned on savings.

Fourteenth, juridical review of lending. Juridically, lending to KJKS is regulated in Law no. 21 of 2008 concerning Sharia Banking and Bank Indonesia Regulation no. 19/1/PBI/2017 concerning Sharia Financial Services Cooperatives. These two regulations provide the legal basis governing the provision of loans to KJKS. The following are several juridical reviews of providing loans to KJKS:

- (1) Lending Requirements. KJKS must ensure that loan disbursement is carried out in accordance with applicable regulations. This includes ensuring that the loan recipient has met the specified requirements, such as having sufficient collateral or collateral and having the ability to repay the loan. KJKS must also ensure that the loan provision does not violate applicable laws and regulations.
- (2) Sharia Principles. Providing loans to KJKS must comply with sharia principles regulated in sharia banking regulations. KJKS must ensure that the provision of loans does not violate sharia principles, such as the principles of justice, transparency and mutual agreement.
- (3) Credit Arrangements. Credit provided by KJKS must be regulated carefully and regularly. KJKS must ensure that the credit granting process complies with applicable regulations, such as Bank Indonesia regulations regarding credit.
- (4) Handling Problem Credit. If problems occur in credit repayment, KJKS must take appropriate action and comply with applicable laws and regulations. KJKS must ensure that problem credit is handled professionally and effectively.

Fifteenth, juridical review of the change in form from BMT to KJKS Legal Entity. BMT or Baitul Maal wat Tamwil is a microfinance institution operating in Indonesia with the aim of helping the economy of small communities by providing affordable financial access. Meanwhile, KJKS or Sharia Financial Services Cooperative is a legal entity that has the same function as BMT, namely providing financial access

to small communities using sharia financial principles. In changing the form from BMT to KJKS, several legal steps must be taken to ensure that the change is carried out legally and in accordance with applicable statutory provisions. Juridically, the change in form from BMT to KJKS must be carried out in accordance with the provisions of Law Number 25 of 1992 concerning Cooperatives and Regulation of the Minister of Cooperatives and SMEs Number 11 of 2015 concerning the Organization and Work Procedures of Sharia Financial Services Cooperatives. Several legal steps that must be taken to change the form of BMT to KJKS are as follows:

- (1) Fulfillment of the requirements for the formation of KJKS. In changing the form from BMT to KJKS, BMT must fulfill the requirements for establishing KJKS in accordance with the provisions of applicable laws and regulations. These requirements include having minimum authorized capital, having adequate membership, having adequate management, and so on.
- (2) Determination of deed of change of form. After BMT fulfills the requirements for establishing a KJKS, a deed of change of form is determined by an authorized notary. This change of form deed will regulate the change in form from BMT to KJKS, including the name, purpose and authorized capital of KJKS.
- (3) Submission of application for change of form. After having the deed of change of form, KJKS must then submit a request for change of form to the Ministry of Cooperatives and SMEs. The application must be accompanied by the necessary documents, such as a deed of change of form, domicile certificate and legal entity certificate.
- (4) KJKS registration. After the request for a change in form is approved, KJKS must then register with the local Cooperative and SME Service. In this registration process, KJKS must complete the necessary documents, such as legal entity legalization letter, deed of establishment, etc.

The research objects include: KJKS An-Nur Jatitujuh Majalengka, KJKS BMT Fastabiq Pati, KJKS BMT Bina Insan Mandiri Tuban, KJKS Al-Abrar, KJKS Nurul Falah, KJKS in East Kalimantan, KJKS UGT BMT Sidogiri KCP Omben, KJKS BMT UGT Sidogiri Pontianak Dahlia Market Branch, KJKS BMT Mandiri Sejahtera Karangcangkring Gresik East Java, KJKS in Mataram City, KJKS BMT Agam Madani Nagari Batu Palano Agam Regency, and KJKS As-Salam Medan.

4.4 Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding innovations carried out by Sharia Financial Services Cooperatives/KJKS

Based on a review of Library Researchs in previous research journals, there are 24 innovations carried out by the Sharia Financial Services Cooperative/KJKS, namely: (1) Financial and non-financial performance towards poverty alleviation; (2) Savings and financing marketing strategy; (3) Information system applications; (4) HR development strategy for management performance; (5) Computerization of service systems; (6) Strategic management; (7) Islamic philanthropy fund management model; (8) Optimizing functions in poverty alleviation; (9) Empowerment of MSMEs according to sharia principles; (10) Training in preparing financial reports using MS

Excel; (11) Assistance in establishing KJKS in dealing with loan sharks; (12) Implementation of Corporate Social Responsibility /CSR; (13) Management of Zakat, Infaq and Sadaqah; (14) Development of dynamic collaboration capabilities to improve business performance; (15) Marketing communication model; (16) Capacity assessment for institutional strengthening; (17) Quality improvement through archive management; (18) The role of social capital at the Sidogiri Islamic boarding school; (19) Sharia investment products to improve savings culture; (20) Contract application; (21) Excel-based accounting bookkeeping design; (22) Cash receipts accounting system; (23) Decision Support System/SPK for providing business capital; and (24) Marketing Strategy.

The research objects include: KJKS BMT Sejahtera Boyolali, KJKS BMT Padang, KJKS Benefit Surabaya, KJKS BMT Bina Ummat Sejahtera KCU Grobogan, KJKS Wanita Melati Harapan, KJKS BMT Marhamah Wonosobo, KJKS Cupak Tengah Village Padang City, KJKS BMT Sejahtera Padang, Village Wuryantoro Lor Wonogiri, KJKS BMT Umat Sejahtera, KJKS BMT Ya Ummi Fatimah Pati, KJKS in Central Java, KJKS in West Java, KJKS BMT Anduring Padang, KJKS Cempaka Putih, KJKS Berkah Madani, KJKS BMT NU Gapura Sumenep, KJKS BMT Mandiri Sejahtera Karangcangkring Gresik, KJKS BMT Barrah City of Tasikmalaya, KJKS BMT La Tansa Gontor Ponorogo.

4.5 Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Sharia Financial Services Cooperative/KJKS Products

Based on a Library Research study in previous research journals, there are (1) cash waqf products; (2) Bai' Bitsaman Ajil Products; (3) Ijarah contract products for multipurpose financing without collateral; (4) Sharia general savings products; (5) Time savings profit sharing products; (6) Kafalah contract products; (7) Farming business financing products; (8) Mudharabah Muqayyadah, Murabahah Bil Wakalah, and Musyarakah financing products for MSMEs; (9) Financing for members; (10) Member wadiah savings products; (11) Business capital financing products; and (12) Qardhu Hasan Products.

The research objects include: KJKS Muamalah Berkah Sejahtera Surabaya, KJKS BMT Bee Mass Ngawi, KJKS BMT UGT Sidogiri Tlanakan Pamekasan Sub-Branch, KJKS BMT Bina Umat Mandiri Adiwerna Branch, KJKS As-Sakinah Kamal Bangkalan, KJKS BMT in West Sumatra, KJKS Mitra Amanah Sejahtera Semarang, KJKS Muamalah Berkah Sejahtera Surabaya, KJKS BMT-UGT Sidogiri Banyuputih Sub-Branch, KJKS BMT Amanah Ummah, KJKS Al-Anshari Bukittinggi, KJKS BMT Mitra Mentari Mersi, KJKS Amanah Mandiri Sekarputih Bagor Nganjuk, KJKS BMT NU Besuki Branch, KJKS BMT IAIN Walisongo Semarang, Karya Usaha Mandiri Syariah Cooperative/KOP KUMS Ciampea District Bogor, KJKS BMT Mardlotillah Tanjungsari Sumedang, KJKS Pilar Mandiri Surabaya, KJKS Paleba.

4.6 Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Financial Performance of Sharia Financial Services Cooperatives/KJKS

Library Research study in previous research journals, there are (1) Accounting treatment for Mudharabah and Murabahah term deposits based on PSAK No. 105; (2) Accounting treatment of PSAK 101 in reporting sources and uses of benevolent funds; (3) Murabahah accounting treatment with PSAK 102 of 2013; (4) Handling Murabahah Non Performing Financing /NPF financing with Mitigation of Risk in Islamic Financial Institutions; (4) Analysis of capital sources, financial reports; (5) 5C principles, including character, capacity, capital, collateral, conditions in financing analysis; (6) Realization of sharia micro financing and its impact on customer business turnover; (7) Fuzzy Tsukamoto and Mamdani method for recommending the value of savings deposits based on average balance; (8) Analysis of liquidity ratios, including: Current Ratio, Cash Ratio; (9) Analysis of solvency ratios, including: Total Debt to Total Asset Ratio, Long Term Debt to Equity Ratio; (10) Profitability ratio analysis, including: Return On Investment, Return On Equity /ROE; (11) C4.5 Algorithm Method in analyzing credit applications; (12) The influence of Good Corporate Governance /GCG, including: transparency, accountability, responsibility, independence, fairness on the level of health; (13) The influence of the marketing mix on increasing sales; (14) The influence of Third Party Funds/DPK, Murabahah financing, Mudharabah financing on profitability; (15) The influence of installment payment patterns and supervision of Murabahah financing on small traders' business profits; and (16) The influence of capital/KPMM, asset quality, management, efficiency, liquidity, independence, growth, corporate identity, compliance with sharia principles, remaining business results/SHU, income, operational costs on the level of soundness.

The research objects include: KJKS BMT in Pematang Regency, KJKS Kalbar Madani Pontianak, KJKS BMT Al-Hayyu Batam City, KJKS BMT Padang City, KJKS BMT Amanah Ummah in Surabaya, KJKS UGT Sidogiri Wirolegi, KJKS BMT At-Taqwa Masjid At- Taqwa Kemanggisan Jakarta, KJKS BMT Al-Makmur Cubadak Lima Kaum Tanah Datar Regency, KJKS using the CAMEL method KJKS Baituttamwil Tamzis Wonosobo, KJKS Ni'mah, KJKS BMT Padang Besi Village, KJKS BMT Kubu Parak Karakah Village, KJKS Muhammad throughout Jabotabek, KJKS West Kalimantan Madani Pontianak, KJKS BMT UGT Sidogiri Koja Branch Jakarta, KJKS Mawar Karanggeneng Lamongan Regency, KJKS Limau Manis Selatan Subdistrict, KJKS Baitul Qiradh in Banda Aceh City, KJKS Kendal Regency, KJKS BMT in Tanah Datar, KJKS BMT El-Tazkiyah Bandung, KJKS Benefits Surabaya, KJKS Kalbar Madani West Kalimantan, KJKS BMT Binamas, KJKS Berkah Madani. KSPPS BMW Ar-Rahmah East Java, KJKS Women in Central Java, KJKS BMT Mandiri Sejahtera Gresik, KJKS BMT Bina Ihsanul Fikri, KJKS BMT Ya Ummi Fatimah, KJKS BMT Nuansa Umat Ngoro Branch, KJKS Mass Group Sragen, KJKS BMT Al Markaz Al Islami Makassar.

4.7 Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Employee Performance in Sharia Financial Services Cooperatives/KJKS

Library Research study in previous research journals, there are 15 employee performances in the Sharia Financial Services Cooperative/KJKS, namely: (1)

Employee Islamic boarding school program; (2) Education and training by local government; (3) Job rotation and transfer; (4) Human Resources; (5) Organizational culture; (6) Employee development through MPAQ; (7) Islamic work ethics; (8) Transformational leadership; (9) Work motivation; (10) Budget participation; (11) Accounting information system; (12) Supervision; (13) Work discipline; (14) Human Resources Management; (15) Understanding of concepts.

The research objects include: KJKS BMT Ya Ummi Fatimah Pati, KJKS BMT Fastabiq Pati, KJKS BMT Precious Metals Grobogan, KJKS BMT TAMZIS Wonosobo, KJKS BMT Bina Ummat Sejahtera CU Lasem in the Rembang Regency Area, KJKS BMT At Taqwa Muhammadiyah, KJKS in Kota Padang.

4.8 Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Determinants of Customer Interest and Satisfaction in Transactions at Sharia Financial Services Cooperatives/KJKS

Based on a Library Research study in previous research journals, there are 28 determinants of customer interest and satisfaction in transactions at the Sharia Financial Services Cooperative/KJKS, namely: (1) Service quality; (2) Benefits; (3) Products; (4) Price; (5) Promotion; (6) Location; (7) Customer orientation; (8) Environmental dynamics; (9) Product innovation; (10) Profit sharing system; (11) Ease of administration; (12) Product knowledge; (13) Trust; (14) Satisfaction; (15) Company image; (16) Communication; (17) Public education; (18) Reference group; (19) Religiosity; (20) Knowledge; (21) Competitive advantage; (22) Marketing Mix; (23) Profit sharing system; (24) Perception of profit; (25) Perception of interest rates; (26) Reference Group; (27) Company perception; (28) Sharia compliance.

The research objects include: KJKS BMT Tumang Boyolali Regency, KJKS BMT Bina Umat Sejahtera Main Branch Tuban Regency, KJKS in Wonosobo, KJKS Arjuna Purwosari Pasuruan, KJKS BMT Al-Falah Batanghari, KJKS BMT TAMZIS Bandung, KJKS BMT-MMU Sidogiri Pasuruan Branch, KJKS BMT Taruna Sejahtera, Bringin Branch, Semarang Regency, KJKS BMT Bina Ummat Sejahtera, Paciran Lamongan Branch, KJKS Halal Cooperative in Samarinda, KJKS BMT Bina Ummat Sejahtera CU Lasem, KJKS BMT in Pekalongan City, KJKS BMT UGT Sidogiri, Kuala Dua Village.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: first, based on mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding Sharia Financial Services Cooperatives (KJKS) during the period 2009 to 2022 originating from the accredited national journal Sinta, there are 142 published journal articles. The Economic Journal is the largest journal publisher that publishes research results regarding KJKS, with 19 articles. The most productive researchers around KJKS are Eni Noor Fitriana, Kevry Ramadany, Dewi Sartika, Ady Wena Pramudya Sukmaningrum, and Puji Sucia, each of whom wrote 2 journal articles. Second, based on the VOSviewer bibliometric study mapping, the network visualization results around KJKS are divided into 5 clusters and 93 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 27

topics, cluster 2 consists of 16 topics, cluster 3 consists of 22 topics, cluster 4 consists of 17 topics, cluster 5 consists of 11 topics. Third, based on the mapping of the Library Research study, there are several topics related to KJKS, namely: (1) Problems with KJKS as many as 15 topics; (2) Innovations carried out by KJKS include 24 topics; (3) KJKS products with 12 topics; (4) KJKS Financial Performance on 16 topics; (5) KJKS employee performance on 15 topics; and (6) Determinants of customer interest and satisfaction in transactions at KJKS on 28 topics.

REFERENCES

- Anwari Wahyuni, khairul; R. (2018). PENGUKURAN KESEHATAN PADA KOPERASI JASA KEUANGAN SYARIAH (KJKS) BERDASARKAN PERATURAN MENTERI NEGARA KOPERASI, USAHA KECIL DAN MENENGAH RI N0.07/Per/Dep.6/IV/2016. *Al-Maslahah*, Vol 14, No 1 (2018), 21–42. <http://jurnal.iainpontianak.or.id/index.php/Almaslahah/article/view/978>
- Dubyna, M., Popelo, O., Kholiavko, N., Zhavoronok, A., Fedyshyn, M., & Yakushko, I. (2022). Mapping the Literature on Financial Behavior: a Bibliometric Analysis Using the VOSviewer Program. *WSEAS Transactions on Business and Economics*, 19(December 2021), 231–246. <https://doi.org/10.37394/23207.2022.19.22>
- El-Halaby, S., Aboul-Dahab, S., & Bin Qoud, N. (2021). A systematic literature review on AAOIFI standards. *Journal of Financial Reporting and Accounting*, 19(2), 133–183. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFRA-06-2020-0170>
- Indriani Shoimatul, A. F. (2020). PENILAIAN TINGKAT KESEHATAN KOPERASI JASA KEUANGAN SYARIAH WANITA. *JIAK: Jurnal Ilmiah Akuntansi Dan Keuangan*, Vol 9 No 1 (2020): *JIAK*, 41–52. <http://journal.stieputrabangsa.ac.id/index.php/jiak/article/view/341>
- Karyadiputra, E. (2016). APLIKASI SISTEM INFORMASI KOPERASI BERBASIS JASA KEUANGAN SYARIAH. *Technologia: Jurnal Ilmiah*, Vol 7, No 3 (2016): *TECHNOLOGIA*. <https://ojs.uniska-bjm.ac.id/index.php/JIT/article/view/628/546>
- Mundir, A. (2016). STRATEGI PENGEMBANGAN KOPERASI JASA KEUANGAN SYARIAH. *MALIA*, Vol 7 No 2 (2016), 265–286.
- Pambudi, A. A. R. K. (2022). PENILAIAN KINERJA KOPERASI JASA KEUANGAN SYARIAH. *Jurnal Ekonomi Integra*, Vol 12, No 2 (2022): *Jurnal Ekonomi Integra*, 203–217. <https://journal.stieip.ac.id/index.php/iga/article/view/215/pdf>
- Rahayu, M. H. R. I. (2021). QADHRU HASAN SEBAGAI MEDIA DALAM MEMBANGUN COSTUMER LOYALTY PADA KOPERASI JASA KEUANGAN SYARIAH. *JURNAL ISLAM NUSANTARA*, Vol 5, No 1 (2021), 1–11. <https://jurnalnu.com/index.php/as/article/view/242/117>
- Sukmaningrum, M. I. R. A. P. S. (2020). THE EFFICIENCY ANALYSIS OF SHARIA

LIFE INSURANCE IN INDONESIA AND FAMILY TAKAFUL IN MALAYSIA USING DATA ENVELOPMENT ANALYSIS METHOD (CASE STUDY ON AL ABRAR'S SHARIAH FINANCIAL SERVICE COOPERATIVE). *Jurnal Ekonomi Syariah Teori Dan Terapan*, Vol. 7 No. 2 (2020): Februari-2020, 319–331. <https://e-journal.unair.ac.id/JESTT/article/view/15558/10872>

van Eck NJ, W. L. (2022). VOSviewer Manual Versi 2.6.18. *Leiden: Univeriteit Leiden*.